

TREATMENT-RESISTANT DEPRESSION AND PSYCHOLOGICAL DEFENSE: CLINICAL PATTERNS

V.K. Abdullaeva¹, R.D. Karimov²

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute^{1,2}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15072015>

Abstract. *The clinical profile of patients with resistant depression exhibited significant diversity in symptoms, comorbidities, and disease progression characteristics. It was found that the intensity of psychological defenses, such as repression and denial, significantly impacts the treatment outcome in patients with resistant depression. Additionally, key predictors of the effectiveness of various therapeutic interventions were identified to optimize treatment strategies.*

Keywords: *resistant depression, clinical features, psychological defense mechanisms.*

The relevance of studying treatment-resistant depression (TRD) is determined by its high prevalence, difficulties in diagnosis and treatment, and the need to develop new therapeutic strategies. In recent years, researchers have focused not only on the biological but also on the psychological aspects of this disorder, allowing for the development of more effective and personalized treatment approaches.

Treatment-resistant depression (TRD) is one of the most challenging forms of depressive disorder, characterized by the persistence of symptoms despite traditional treatment methods, including pharmacotherapy, psychotherapy, and other interventions. Studies indicate that up to 30% of patients with depression experience a resistant form, significantly complicating the diagnostic and therapeutic process. The increasing number of patients with depressive disorders makes the issue of treatment resistance even more urgent.

The factors contributing to treatment resistance are multifaceted and may include genetic, biochemical, psychological, and social aspects. Neurobiological mechanisms, such as dysfunctions of the serotonergic and dopaminergic systems, abnormalities in the prefrontal cortex, as well as cognitive and psycho-emotional characteristics, play a key role in the development of resistance to standard therapy. Despite the widespread use of antidepressants and psychotherapeutic methods, TRD remains a major challenge in psychiatry, as a significant number of patients do not respond adequately to treatment. This leads to prolonged illness, an increased risk of suicidal behavior, and a reduced quality of life.

Current research is focused on developing new therapeutic approaches, such as transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS), electroconvulsive therapy (ECT), and innovative pharmacological treatments. However, their long-term efficacy and safety still require further investigation.

Increasing attention is being paid to the psychological aspects of TRD, particularly the role of defense mechanisms, as well as the cognitive and emotional characteristics of patients. Studies show that defense mechanisms such as repression and denial can exacerbate the course of the disorder and reduce the effectiveness of standard treatment methods. Understanding these processes is crucial for improving psychotherapeutic strategies and enhancing treatment efficacy.

Psychological defense in the context of depression represents a set of unconscious mechanisms aimed at reducing anxiety and mitigating internal conflicts. Patients with depression often exhibit distortions in self-perception and their view of the surrounding world, which may be

linked to the activation of defense strategies. In cases of TRD, such mechanisms may become overly pronounced, hindering effective treatment and recovery. For example, symptom denial, excessive rationalization of the causes of the disorder, or externalization of guilt may reduce patient motivation for therapy and complicate the recovery process.

The study of these mechanisms can contribute to the individualization of treatment and a deeper understanding of the causes of chronic depression. Many patients with TRD exhibit increased resistance to emotional experiences, which may lead to a weakened or delayed therapeutic response. This resistance is often associated with the use of defense mechanisms such as emotional suppression or symptom avoidance.

Understanding how patients employ psychological defense mechanisms can improve psychotherapeutic approaches. Methods aimed at identifying and processing defense mechanisms can significantly enhance treatment success, facilitate deeper work on depressive symptoms, and reduce the likelihood of relapse.

The aim of this study is to analyze the clinical characteristics and psychological mechanisms in patients with treatment-resistant depression, as well as to identify key factors influencing the effectiveness of various therapeutic approaches to improve treatment strategies.

Material and methods. As part of this study, 46 randomly selected patients diagnosed with treatment-resistant depression (TRD) were examined. These patients had not responded to first-line antidepressant treatment for at least six weeks. All participants provided informed consent to participate in the study, which complied with ethical standards. Patients were informed about the study's objectives, methods, potential risks and benefits, as well as their right to data confidentiality. The age range of participants was between 25 and 55 years, including 26 women and 20 men. The diagnosis of depression was established using a structured clinical interview and met the ICD-10 criteria for depressive spectrum disorders. Additionally, the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAMD) was used to assess the severity of depressive symptoms at baseline and throughout the observation period.

To study patients' psychological defense mechanisms, a methodology developed by V.V. Rozenbaum was employed. This method includes the assessment of primary defense mechanisms such as repression, projection, denial, rationalization, and regression. It allows for the evaluation of the intensity of these mechanisms in each patient and their impact on depressive states. The Defense Style Questionnaire (DSQ) was also used to classify the types of defense mechanisms utilized by the patients. The level of social support and stress in patients' lives was assessed using a self-report scale measuring stress levels and perceived social support. As part of the study, all patients underwent a course of cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) aimed at identifying and modifying maladaptive defense mechanisms. A key aspect of the therapy was addressing unconscious psychological defenses that contributed to the persistence of depression, as well as analyzing and restructuring destructive thought patterns. All collected data were analyzed using statistical methods, including descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation), an independent-sample t-test to compare group differences, and correlation analysis to examine the relationship between the severity of psychological defenses and treatment outcomes. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussion. As a result of the study, a dataset was obtained that allowed for the assessment of the impact of psychological defense mechanisms on depressive symptoms in patients with treatment-resistant depression, as well as on the effectiveness of cognitive-behavioral

therapy (CBT). Including characteristics such as age, gender, duration of illness, and the number of treatment attempts is essential for analyzing factors that may influence the clinical manifestations and treatment effectiveness of treatment-resistant depression (Table 1).

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of Patients

Parameter	Value
Total number of patients	46
Age (mean ± standard deviation)	42.3 ± 8.6 years
Gender	
- Male	20 (43.5%)
- Female	26 (56.5%)
Duration of illness (years)	2.5 ± 1.3 years
Number of treatment attempts (mean)	2.3 ± 0.9 attempts

In this study, the higher proportion of women in the sample (56.5% vs. 43.5%) may be attributed to the fact that depression is generally more frequently diagnosed in women.

All examined patients reported a prolonged period of depressed mood that persisted despite attempts at treatment with antidepressants (Figure 1). Figure 1 illustrates the prevalence of the main clinical symptoms of depression among the 46 patients with treatment-resistant depression.

The most common symptoms include depressed mood (97.8%), apathy (91.3%), fatigue and weakness (87.0%), and insomnia (82.6%). Suicidal thoughts were reported by 65.2% of patients, highlighting the severity of the disorder. Appetite disturbances were present in 54.3% of patients, which is also a characteristic manifestation of depression.

Physical symptoms such as headaches (40% of patients), back and joint pain (28% of patients), chronic fatigue, and dyspepsia were observed in a significant proportion of patients. Additionally, 56.5% (26 patients) reported difficulties with concentration and decision-making, significantly impairing their daily activities and work performance.

These findings indicate that treatment-resistant depression is characterized by pronounced and multifaceted symptoms that substantially impact patients' quality of life.

Figure 1. Major clinical symptoms of depression

The use of the Defense Style Questionnaire (DSQ) allowed for the classification of defense mechanisms among patients. The primary defense mechanisms identified in the participants included repression, denial, rationalization, and projection.

- 36.9% of patients (n = 17) used repression as their primary defense mechanism.
- 23.9% of patients (n = 11) actively relied on denial.
- 19.6% of patients (n = 9) utilized rationalization.
- 19.6% of patients (n = 9) employed projection.

A correlation analysis revealed that the severity of repression ($r = 0.57, p < 0.01$) and denial ($r = 0.63, p < 0.01$) was associated with higher depression scores on the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAMD). Patients who predominantly used repression and denial exhibited higher depression scores both before and after therapy, indicating that these defense mechanisms hinder the recovery process. Projection and rationalization also showed a moderate correlation with depressive symptoms, but to a lesser extent than repression and denial. Notably, the use of rationalization had a weaker association with depressive symptoms ($r = 0.31, p < 0.05$). A moderate negative correlation was found between depression reduction and the severity of defense mechanisms ($r = -0.45, p < 0.05$). To assess treatment effectiveness, all patients underwent a course of cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT). The Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAMD) was used to measure changes in depressive symptoms before and after therapy.

Based on the analysis of CBT outcomes in relation to defense mechanisms, patients were divided into two groups: group 1 – patients with pronounced defense mechanisms (repression and denial): 60.9% (n = 28), group 2 – patients with less pronounced defense mechanisms (rationalization, projection): 39.1% (n = 18). The mean reduction in depression scores on the HAMD scale was: 8.1 ± 2.7 points in group 1 and 11.3 ± 2.3 points in group 2. The difference between groups was statistically significant ($t = 2.94, p < 0.01$), suggesting that patients with less pronounced defense mechanisms respond more effectively to CBT.

A high level of social support proved to be an important predictor of positive treatment outcomes in patients with treatment-resistant depression. Using the self-assessment scale for stress and social support, an additional correlation analysis was conducted with treatment results. It was found that patients with high social support ($r = -0.45, p < 0.05$) and low stress levels ($r = -0.41, p < 0.05$) demonstrated better therapeutic outcomes. These patients experienced greater reductions in depressive symptoms compared to those with higher stress levels and limited social support.

Conclusion. The study results confirmed that the intensity of psychological defense mechanisms, such as repression and denial, significantly affects the treatment outcomes of patients with treatment-resistant depression. Patients who predominantly rely on these defense mechanisms exhibit lower therapeutic progress, highlighting the need for tailored treatment strategies. In contrast, patients with less pronounced defense mechanisms, such as rationalization and projection, demonstrated a more significant positive response to cognitive-behavioral therapy. These findings emphasize the importance of an integrated approach to the treatment of treatment-resistant depression, incorporating not only pharmacological and psychotherapeutic methods but also considering individual psychological characteristics and the level of social support.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullaeva V.K., Abbasova D.S., Sulstonova K.B. et al. Predict depressive disorders at the earliest stages of its formation in adolescents // *Annali d/ Italia* – 2020. – VOL 1, № 7; pp 15-18.
2. Abdullaeva V.K, Nurkhodjaev S.N. Optimization of Therapy of Treatment Resistant Depressions in patients taking into account Personal Characteristics. *Jornal of Research in health science*, 67-72,2019.
3. Bauer, M., et al. (2021). Treatment-resistant depression: Treatment options and strategies. *Therapeutic Advances in Psychopharmacology*, 11:2045125321990786. DOI: 10.1177/2045125321990786
4. Barton, D. A., et al. (2019). The role of biological mechanisms in treatment-resistant depression. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 10: 678. DOI: 10.3389/fpsyt.2019.00678
5. Fava, M. (2020). Management of Treatment-Resistant Depression. *The New England Journal of Medicine*. 382(15): 1420-1428.
6. McAllister-Williams, R.H., et al. (2021). New and emerging therapies for treatment-resistant depression. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, 35(4): 387-404.
7. Muench, U., et al. (2020). Psychological interventions in treatment-resistant depression. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 266: 365-374.
8. Moroz, I.L., et al. (2022). Cognitive and emotional features of patients with treatment-resistant depression. *Psychiatry Research*, 302: 114049.
9. Nurkhodjaev S., Babarakhimova S., Abdullaeva V. Early Detection and Prevention of Suicidal Behavior in Adolescents – *Indian Journal of Forensic Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science No 96/2022 37 medicine & Toxicology*. VOL 14, № 3(2020) pp.7258- 7263.
10. Rush, A.J., et al. (2019). Acute and longer-term outcomes in treatment-resistant depression: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 80(3): e1-e9.
11. Sultanov Sh.H., Tursunkhodzhaeva L.A., Khodzhaeva N.I., Abdullaeva V.K., Nurkhodjaev S.N. Diagnostics of Dysthymic Disorders and Therapy of Patients with Opium Addiction with Anxiety-Depressive Variant of Post-Withdrawal Syndrome // *International Journal of Current Research and Review*, Vol 12, Issue 23, 142-147, 2020.
12. Sultanov Sh., Talimbekov O., Khodjaeva N., Abdullaeva V. Predictors for the formation of dysthymic disorders. *Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science No 96/2022*, p.34-37.
13. Vasila K. Abdullaeva, Botir T. Daminov, Abdulaziz A. Nasirov, Janna T. Rustamova, Yen., 2020. Features of affective disorders and compliance of patients with chronic renal failure receiving replacement therapy by hemodialysis. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research No. 4(12)*. – P.531-535.